

Pest management and control WEEDS

Biological control of weeds in rice, Cuttack, India

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In an experiment on the biological control of weeds during the 1978 dry season, *Altica cyanea* Web., commonly known as the steel blue beetle, was released on *Ludwigia perennis* L., a common weed in rice, in both field and cage treatments.

In the field, beetles were released in plots planted with 100 plants each of rice, sedges, *Sphenoclea zeylanica*

Gaertn., and *L. perennis*. All weeds were planted separately except *L. perennis*, which also was interplanted between rice rows. Three replications were made.

A large number (uncounted) of beetles were released at 5 p.m. Observation of beetle damage was at 9 a.m. the next day. *L. perennis* were completely denuded within 16 hours. Each plant was loaded with beetles. Rice plants were not harmed, although beetles were found resting on them.

Only 5 of 300 *L. perennis* plants regenerated 3 months after treatment, with 1.7% bud resurgence.

In nethouse conditions, 25 weed plants were planted on trays in 5 glass cages. Four levels of beetle infestation were used — 25, 50, 75, and 100. The load of beetles affected denuding time and resurgence ability.

Beetles consumed weeds faster in the field than in cages. Younger weed plants were preferred. Larvae also were observed feeding on weeds. Because the beetle prefers nonrice plants and multiplies rapidly, investigations on the biological control of *Altica cyanea* in rice fields should include techniques of large-scale multiplication and field release. ■

Early crop weeding and weed growth and grain yield of third crop

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An important rainfed or partially irrigated cropping pattern in Bangladesh is rice - rice - nonrice crop. The first rice crop is dry-seeded, the second is transplanted, and the third nonrice crop is established on residual soil moisture or is partially irrigated. Under this pattern, weed problems in the first rice crop are acute and in the second crop are moder-

ate. In the nonrice crop, weeds cause some yield reduction. Farmers do varying degrees of weed control in the two rice crops, but usually do no weed control in the third crop.

This experiment studied the impact of weeding regime in the two rice crops on weed growth and grain yields of the nonrice crop. A randomized complete block design with 3 replications was used. Land preparation was done plot by plot. First crop treatments were assigned at random and treatments were maintained in the second crop. The third crop was not weeded. All recommended management practices except weeding were followed. Plot sizes were 15 m × 4 m in the first and second crops

and 5 m × 4 m in the third crop. Grain samples were taken from 4 m × 3 m per plot and weed samples at harvest were taken from 3 places in each plot, using 0.5 × 0.5 m quadrats.

Weed weight at harvest and grain yields of the third nonrice crops were unaffected by the weeding regime applied to the two rice crops (see table). When better weed control measures were applied to the first and second crops, actual weed weight was slightly reduced and grain yields were slightly increased in all three crops tested.

Weeds common to all three crops are *Echinochloa colona* (L. Link), *Cyperus iria* L., and *Fimbristylis littoralis* Gaud. ■

Weed weight at harvest and grain yields of nonrice crops after weeding of two rice crops. BRRI, 1980-81. ^a

Weeding regime ^b		Third crop (winter 1980-81)					
First crop (dry-seeded rice, 1980)	Second crop (transplanted rice, 1980)	Millet		Gram		Soybean	
		Weed wt (g/0.25 m ²)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Weed wt (g/0.25 m ²)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Weed wt (g/0.25 m ²)	Grain yield (kg/ha)
No weeding	No weeding	11.1 a	826 a	11.2 a	421 a	9.9 a	1455 a
Butachlor 2.0 kg a.i./ha, one hand weeding 3 WE	Hand weeding 3 WT	10.0 a	854 a	7.5 a	440 a	9.2 a	1471
Hand weeding 2, 5, and 8 WE	Hand weeding 3 and 5 WT	8.1 a	883 a	6.4 a	431 a	8.6 a	1468 a

^a Av of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by common letters do not differ significantly at the 5% level. ^b fb = followed by, WE = weeks after emergence, WT = weeks after transplanting.